

Parents' Attitudes Towards Early Childhood Distance Learning In Light Of E-Learning Standards During The Corona Pandemic In The Al-Ahsa Region

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 12, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : E-Learning, E-Learning Standards, Early Childhood Stage</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5191579</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the parent's attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region through the following variables (type of education, stage the child is studying, kinship, type of school) , The two researchers used a questionnaire consisting of seven areas: (leadership, technology, rehabilitation and support, design, interaction, Justice and accessibility, measurement and evaluation) distributed over (38) paragraphs , The study showed that there were no significant differences due to the study variables on the seven domains, with the exception of the field of measurement and evaluation and in favor of government schools, The study recommended the importance of providing appropriate courses to develop the technological efficiency for students, parents and teachers on an ongoing basis to keep abreast of the latest developments in the crisis.</i></p>

Introduction

The Corona pandemic imposed many challenges on the education systems in most countries of the world, which led to the closure of schools and universities and the suspension of studies in attendance, Therefore, these countries resorted to the second option, which is distance education, to ensure the continuity and management of the teaching and learning process Distance education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia plays an essential role in the life and culture of Saudi society Through its application of the national standards for e-learning in the Kingdom These standards are a document and guide for controlling the quality of e-learning in schools and public education institutions in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as it is a means of measuring the practices applied by educational institutions in the Kingdom and determining the degree of achieving these standards.

The Adteck team on education affairs of the World Bank confirmed that distance education is the best method of education during the Corona pandemic for all educational materials and at all stages, which provides advantages that drive the continuity of education and improve the learner's attitudes towards the educational situation (World Bank Edteck Teem, 2020: 5- 10).

In this regard, (UNESCO, 2020) indicated that the goal of using technology and communication must achieve the goals of education, and for this to be achieved, standards and indicators must be provided to measure the quantity and quality of outputs that will be achieved by distance education.

Daradkeh (2013) indicates that the success of the educational process and its fulfillment of its mission depends on its organic association with the institutions of society, especially the family, because one of its duties is to carry out effective activities to build a close relationship with parents.

The success of distance education is not limited to teachers, students and those in charge of the educational process, so the views of students' parents must be integrated as they are the most important elements of the educational process (Leontyeva, 2018).

David et al. 2020 confirms that despite the opportunities and benefits offered by distance education during the Corona pandemic, the (Covid-19) crisis created obstacles as a result of the use of distance education platforms, and the most prominent of these obstacles :Difficulty in measuring the results of distance learning due to the poor management of it remotely in addition to the slow progress of students in educational curricula, especially primary school students and students with low achievement and internet outage The disparity in financial capabilities among students' parents to secure portable computer devices for their children or the Internet for each individual in light of the low financial income and weak technological skills for some parents, teachers and students David added that among the obstacles are also the distractions in the home that surround the learner during the distance learning process, and the lack of some learners' sense of responsibility and seriousness towards this type of education because it adds new tasks and the difficulty of matching them to all curricula in this type of education.

The distance education pattern came with a decision by the Saudi authorities, at the beginning of the Corona pandemic

The Saudi Ministry of Education announced that, in accordance with the preventive and precautionary measures recommended by the competent health authorities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as part of its tireless efforts to control the new Corona virus (COVID19) and prevent its entry and spread.

And based on the concern to protect the health of male and female students and the educational and administrative staff in public and university education and to ensure their safety. It was decided to temporarily suspend the study in all regions and governorates of the Kingdom, starting from Monday, Rajab 14, 1441 AH, until further notice, the decision included schools and institutions of public, private and university education, and the General Organization for Technical and Vocational Training, both governmental and private.

The Minister of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia directed the activation of virtual schools and distance education during the suspension period, in order to ensure the continuation of the educational process in an effective and quality manner, as the competent committee in the Ministry decided to follow up on the developments of the Corona virus, according to the following:

- Supervising offices begin their work during the suspension period to follow up the educational process, coordinate distance education procedures, and respond to parents' inquiries.

- Ensuring the functioning of the virtual school during the suspension period through the means of distance learning provided by the Ministry of Education, through the virtual school platform (Vschool.sa), and the use of digital enrichment materials through the website and application located in the App Store for Apple and Android under the name (Unified Education System).

- Providing lessons for all academic levels asynchronously, through the Ain TV. Channel.

Universities, the General Organization for substantive and Technical Training and the National Center for E-Learning complete the requirements for distance education for all male and female students.

Currently, the Saudi authorities have announced arrangements for the Re-education in schools and universities for the academic year 2021-2022. after the Ministry of Education agreed with the Ministry of Health, it approved a plan for the return of education, which includes four basic points, to ensure the continuation of the educational process in line with the requirements of public safety in light of the Corona pandemic.

The arrangements stipulate that faculty members will return "to workplaces in schools, colleges, universities, institutes and vocational training institutions," and they will have to take full doses of Corona vaccines, which will be a requirement to enter these buildings, and this will be confirmed using the "Tawakalna" and "tabadna" applications, as the health safety of students will be required before they return to the study seats.

Study problem and questions:

After the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia took several precautionary measures to combat the spread of the Corona virus and confront the education system to the great challenge that led to the launch of distance education programs despite the refusal and opposition of some parents to use distance education despite the advantages achieved by this system in addition, the conditions of the spread of the epidemic did not allow the Education Department to hold training courses to help parents deal with this system and to clarify the idea that this system is suitable for all educational materials and stages, including early childhood . From here emerged the problem of the current study, which came to identify the reality of distance education for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic from the point of view of parents, and to assess the quality of this education through the capabilities and technologies that the Kingdom provides to its schools, through :

Answer the following study questions:

1- What are the attitudes of parents towards distance learning for early childhood in light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region?

2- Are there any statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the averages of the parents' responses. Attributed to the variables of the study (type of education: diploma and less, Bachelor's, postgraduate studies, stage taught by the child: kindergarten, primary grades. kinship: mother, father, other. School type: government education, private education)?

Study Objectives:

The current study sought to achieve the following objectives :

1- Identifying parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region.

2- To identify the differences between the average responses of parents of children in early childhood that are attributed to the study variables (type of education: diploma or less, bachelor's, postgraduate studies, stage taught by the child: kindergarten, primary grades. Kinship : mother, father, other School type: public education, private education.

The importance of studying

The importance of the current study is as follows:

- The importance of this study comes from the importance of the subject. Knowing the reality of the quality of distance education for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia constitutes the actual knowledge of this type of education and for this important stage of education, which is a basic stage in the educational ladder, In addition to the desire of the two researchers to communicate the views of the study sample to officials and decision-makers based on the development of the educational process, and it is hoped that the results of this study will benefit teachers and researchers about the efficiency of this distance education system. The two researchers hope that this study will constitute a cognitive and theoretical addition in the field of distance education in early childhood stage.

Procedural terms and definitions

Quality of education: It is the process that aims to improve the educational process and achieve a qualitative leap through By applying a package of educational procedures and systems and documentation of the various educational programs, so that this improvement in the educational process is done by raising the different levels of students, and the quality of education is not limited to students only, It also includes different aspects such as the teacher, the curriculum, the school community and the surrounding environment. Amer (2014).

The two researchers define the quality of education procedurally: it is a set of standards, procedures and decisions whose implementation aims to improve the educational environment, and it is a reference for controlling the quality of aspects of education and e-training.

These standards include educational institutions and the conditions of individuals who have a direct or indirect relationship with the educational system, It is measured by the degree that the respondent obtains on the study tool consisting of the following areas: (leadership, technology, rehabilitation and support, design, interaction, Justice and accessibility, measurement and evaluation).

Distance education: It is a modern educational system and style that focuses on providing educational opportunities to learners through educational means, technologies and platforms available on the Internet and modern technologies supported by audio, video and printed data (Bozkurt, 2019).

E-Learning Standards: It is a document issued by the National Center for E-Learning and represents a guide for controlling the quality of e-learning. It includes two sections: Standards for entities, which include standards for leadership, technology, qualification and support, and consists of 28 sub-standards. The second section is program standards, and it consists of four standards: design, interaction, justice, accessibility, measurement and evaluation. (National Center for E-Learning, 2020).

Previous studies

The two researchers dealt with studies related to the subject, which are:

- Al-Enezi study (2020), which aimed to identify the attitudes of parents towards the role of the distance learning system in teaching Arabic to students of foreign private schools during the Corona crisis in the State of Kuwait, the researcher used the questionnaire as a tool for the study, and the study sample consisted of (273) parents the results indicated that there were differences between parents' attitudes due to the kinship variable and in favor of the mothers, and there were no significant differences due to the educational level variable and the stage in which the child was studying.

- Abu Ababa study (2020), which sought to evaluate the experience of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in distance education in light of the Corona pandemic from the parent's point of view in the city of Riyadh, the researcher used the descriptive analytical method and the questionnaire as a tool to collect data from a sample of (310) parents, and the results indicated that the distance learning experience was successful and came to a high degree.

- Malkawi study (2020), which aimed to identify the reality of distance education and its challenges in Jordan during the Corona pandemic from the parent's point of view, and the study sample reached (135) parents, the study used the descriptive analytical method and the questionnaire as a tool for the study, the results indicated that the reality of distance education during the Corona pandemic from the parents' point of view came to a medium degree, and there were no significant differences due to a variable related to kinship.

- The study of Al-Maliki, Haifa, Daghestani, Balqis (2020), which aimed to identify the role of electronic educational platforms in the professional growth of kindergarten teachers. The descriptive survey method was used to answer the questions of the study.. The sample size was (205) kindergarten teachers. the study found that kindergarten teachers' practice of electronic platforms amounted to (87.2%) when providing a flexible learning environment and using more than one way to display information, The study also showed that there are obstacles in the teachers' use of electronic platforms, including the lack of financial resources, the weakness of the Internet within the school, the large number of tasks and roles of the supervisory teacher, and the weakness of special training programs.

- Foti study (Foti, 2020) aimed at exploring perceptions, possibilities and limitations related to the implementation of distance education in kindergartens during the Corona pandemic period, and the study used the questionnaire as a tool for data collection, The results indicated that the teachers responded to apply of distance education in order to maintain communication with their students, and to respond to helping the Greek family in educating its children.

- The study of Basilaia and Kvadza (2020), which aimed to identify the attitudes and opinions of parents towards the rapid transition to distance education in the State of Georgia , The study used the analytical inductive method, and the study sample consisted of (950) students and parents, and the results indicated that the attitudes of students and their parents towards the use of distance education during the Corona crisis were successful and constitute a precedent for overcoming educational obstacles during this pandemic, and the results also showed that the most prominent Obstacles to this method of education is the children's feeling of boredom while receiving their lessons.

- Swed & Jihan Study (2020)

The study aimed to know the reality of distance education in light of the spread of the Corona virus and its impact on parents of school students , The researcher used the documentary descriptive approach by analyzing the events of the pandemic and its most important data. The researcher concluded that the psychological impact of the pandemic on parents was very large, as many parents do not prefer to continue distance education regardless of the side effects. The study also concluded that continuous educational support must be provided to parents to ensure the success of the educational process. The researcher recommended the importance of holding encouraging training courses for parents before starting e-learning, in addition to the need to pay attention to the sector of parents and work to reduce the burden on them. Finally, the researcher recommended the importance of continuing distance education even after the return of in-person education to ensure the continuation of the educational process at any time.

- The study of Al-Qahtani, Amal, Al-Shehhi, Hayat, Bin Nasser, Alia, Embassy, Azza (2020)

The study aimed to know the motivation and its role in activating the distance learning process among basic education students in light of the Corona pandemic from the point of view of parents and teachers. The researchers used the descriptive analytical approach on a sample of (330), and the study reached the satisfaction of parents with regard to the quality of education during the Corona pandemic and that teachers' keenness to communicate and interact with students during distance education and provide them with feedback increases their educational levels. Finally, the study recommended the generalization of the trend using distance education after the end of the pandemic, in addition to the presence education, and the need for continuous communication between the teacher and parents to increase their involvement in the education process, in addition to providing intensive training for both the teacher and the guardian in communicating via electronic platforms.

- The Qur'an study (2021), which aimed to identify the reality of e-learning in light of the Corona pandemic among Riyadh children from the teachers' point of view in the Directorate of Education in Irbid Governorate – Jordan and to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the questionnaire as a tool for collecting data from a sample of (211) teachers who were selected by the simple random method , And the results showed that the estimates of the reality of e-learning in light of the Corona pandemic in kindergartens from the teachers' point of view in the Directorate of Education in Irbid Governorate - Jordan came to a medium degree, the results also indicated that there are differences due to the type of kindergarten and in favor of private kindergartens, and there are differences due to the educational qualification variable and in favor of higher studies.

- Timmons, Cooper, Bozek & Braund, 2021 which aimed to identify the impact of the Covid-19 epidemic in early childhood on e-learning, and the qualitative approach was used to answer the questions of the study , The study concluded that parents see themselves as having clearly improved in dealing with technology and smart devices. The results also showed that there are great concerns from parents about the lack of fairness and justice in e-learning among children, In addition to the lack of resources and sometimes the lack of internet, the study recommended that both parents and teachers should receive training in the use of technology before reopening schools, in addition to activating the community partnership between companies and other institutions. The study also recommended that children who are slow to learn should be given additional lessons to avoid any problem in learning and to achieve justice among children.

Method and Procedure

Study Approach

The two researchers adopted the descriptive approach using a questionnaire.

study population and sample

The study population consisted of all parents of children in early childhood in Al-Ahsa region.

The study sample

The study was applied to a random sample of (130) individuals from the parents of children in the kindergarten and primary grades who are enrolled in early childhood schools and kindergartens for the study year 1442-1443 AH, and table (1) shows the study sample

Variable	level	number
the level	Diploma and less	21
	Bachelor	89
	Postgraduate	20
Stage	Kindergarten	52
	Primary classes	78

Kinship	Mother	94
	Father	14
	Other	22
School	government education	87
	private education	43

study tool

In order to achieve the objectives of the current study, the two researchers designed the questionnaire with reference to the theoretical literature and e-learning standards in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: The first relates to the primary data of the study sample members: (educational level, educational stage, kinship relationship, and type of education) distributed over seven areas: (leadership, technology, rehabilitation and support, design, interaction, Justice and accessibility, measurement and evaluation). The questionnaire items were designed according to the five-point Likert scale (strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neutral, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree) and the study adopted the following weights (3,68-5) high, (3.67-2,34) medium, (2,33-1) is weak.

The validity of the study tool

First: The sincerity of the arbitrators

To achieve the validity of the tool, the two researchers designed the questionnaire electronically and sent it to a number of arbitrators specialized in the field of early childhood, curricula, teaching and educational techniques , Based on what the arbitrators agreed upon, the two researchers reformulated some paragraphs and modified them so that the study tool consisted of (38) paragraphs distributed over 7 areas.

Second: Structural validity “consistency validity:”

Consistency validity:

The study tool was applied to an exploratory sample from outside the study sample consisting of (25) from outside the study sample, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between the paragraph and the total score of the domain to which it belongs, and between the paragraph, the field, the total degree, and the table (2) shows that:

Table (2)

Pearson correlation coefficient between the paragraph and the total score for the domain to which it belongs, and between the item, the domain and the total score

	Domain - Paragraphs	Pearson's paragraph-to-domain correlation coefficient	Statistical significance	Pearson's correlation coefficient, item and domain, with the total score	Statistical significance
	Leadership			.733**	.000
1	My child's school follows the e-learning strategy approved by the competent authorities	.688**	.000	.576**	.003
2	My child's teacher strives to update content and activities without violating national laws and policies	.834**	.000	.601**	.001
3	My child's teacher uses e-learning applications efficiently to help the learner achieve international learning standards.	.845**	.000	.536**	.006
4	My Child's Teacher provides student-centered learning opportunities in line with modern educational philosophies.	.863**	.000	.621**	.001
5	My child's teacher uses multiple measurement tools to measure learners' progress.	.749**	.000	.503*	.010
6	My child's teacher sets the exact time plan for all the steps that the learner is expected to carry it out.	.612**	.001	.493*	.012
7	My child's teacher adheres to the comprehensive assessment criteria for distance learning.	.634**	.001	.496*	.012
	Technology			.885**	.000

8	My child's school provides in its electronic system the electronic alert feature to constantly alert learners	.865**	.000	.796**	.000
9	The teacher encourages my child to use the e-learning system through his smart phone.	.913**	.000	.731**	.000
10	My child's teacher is keen to follow the interaction of learners to obtain data through the distance education system.	.757**	.000	.685**	.000
11	My child's teacher uses the right app for slow learners.	.899**	.000	.731**	.000
12	My child's teacher carries out the appropriate and required tests through the distance learning system.	.739**	.000	.525**	.007
13	My child's teacher is keen on how to securely enter the distance learning system	.489*	.013	.629**	.001
	Rehabilitation and support		.000	.762**	.000
14	My child's teacher encourages me to take advantage of parenting programs in the use of technology and distance learning skills.	.885**	.000	.662**	.000
15	Educational institutions provide training for me in the use of technology and e-learning platforms.	.946**	.000	.722**	.000
16	My child's teacher encourages my child to provide appropriate technical and educational assistance throughout the learning process.	.935**	.000	.723**	.000
	the design			.901**	.000
17	My child's teacher is keen to keep the goals of electronic content clear.	.794**	.000	.725**	.000
18	My child's teacher adheres to the universal design standards for electronic content.	.787**	.000	.679**	.000
19	My child's teacher breaks the content into small, reusable pieces.	.784**	.000	.756**	.000
20	My child's teacher provides electronic content in various forms (texts, presentations, audio materials, etc.).	.736**	.000	.679**	.000
21	My child's teacher prepares the content in different designs in terms of colour, shape and size, which reduces effort.	.801**	.000	.715**	.000
22	My child's teacher presents the electronic educational content in an organized manner and easy to navigate between its parts.	.810**	.000	.745**	.000
23	My child's teacher is keen on evaluating the learners and adding comments on the educational content of the electronic course.	.849**	.000	.726**	.000
	Interaction			.692**	.000
24	My child's teacher encourages him to help him read instructions on how to start using the e-learning system and enter the lessons.	.641**	.001	.496*	.012
25	My child's teacher sets the timelines for all the steps that learners are expected to	.797**	.000	.796**	.000

	perform for each electronic unit.				
26	My child's teacher is always keen to answer learners' inquiries.	.917**	.000	.498*	.011
27	My child's teacher provides feedback to learners on tasks completed on an ongoing basis.	.529**	.007	.679**	.000
28	My child's teacher employs self-assessment techniques for learners to check their progress.	.814**	.000	.593**	.002
29	My child's teacher employs methods to measure learners' interaction and engagement during the educational presentation.	.917**	.000	.498*	.011
	Justice and accessibility			.797**	.000
30	My child's teacher helps me possess the minimum knowledge, technical skills and competencies required to pursue my child in e-learning	.948**	.000	.437*	.029
31	The distance learning system provides my child with access to all programs that serve the learning and education process	.757**	.000	.715**	.000
32	The distance learning system provides my child with easy techniques and ways to obtain them	.745**	.000	.489*	.013
33	The distance learning system allows the presentation of electronic content in multiple audio-visual ways	.871**	.000	.441*	.027
	Measurement and Evaluation			.697**	.000
34	My child's teacher employs learning measurement tools that are appropriate to the activities and resources of electronic content.	.807**	.000	.605**	.001
35	Learning system shows distance degrees policy evaluation of electronic courses.	.868**	.000	.623**	.001
36	My child's teacher sets descriptive criteria associated with the grading policy for evaluate learner performance.	.909**	.000	.536**	.006
37	The distance learning system provides a mechanism to measure the degree of beneficiaries' satisfaction with the e-learning style of providing the material.	.849**	.000	.621**	.001
38	I have the opportunity to evaluate the electronic courses that my child is constantly studying.	.760**	.000	.536**	.006

* Statistical significant at the significance level (0.05).

** Statistical significant at the level of significance (0.01).

It is clear from Table (2) that the values of the Pearson correlation coefficients between the paragraphs of the questionnaire and the total degree of the domain to which it belongs are statistically significant at the significance level (0.01) or (0.05), and this indicates that all the questionnaire statements have a degree of sincerity, which indicates that the validity of the tool for measuring what it was prepared for.

Stability:

To calculate the values of the scale stability coefficient, the researcher applied the questionnaire to the Survey Sample consisting of (25), and the values of the reliability coefficient were calculated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Cronbach's Alpha and Table No. (3) show the stability coefficients of the tool fields and the total degree of the tool:

Table (3)

Cronbach's alpha stability coefficients for the domains of the early childhood distance education quality questionnaire in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from the parents' point of view and the total

The Domain	Cronbach's alpha stability coefficients
Domain One: Leadership	0.87
Domain Two: Technology	0.86
Domain Three: Rehabilitation and Support	0.91
Fourth Domain: Design	0.90
Fifth Domain: Interaction	0.84
Domain Six: Justice and accessibility	0.82
Seventh Domain: Measurement and Evaluation	0.89
Total marks	0.96

It is clear from Table (3) that the stability coefficient of the quality of distance education questionnaire for early childhood in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from the parents' point of view was (0.96), and the stability coefficients on the domains ranged (0.82 -0.91), which indicates that the tool has high stability.

Statistical methods:

To answer the study questions, the researcher used a number of statistical methods to apply them in the SPSS statistical analysis program version (23) where it was extracted:

Arithmetic mean, and standard deviations to answer the first question, and analysis of variance was used to answer the second question.

The results of the arithmetic mean value were interpreted in a scale according to the five-point scale that was used in the current study:

- The range is calculated, $5-1=4$

- The category length is calculated by dividing the range by the number of categories according to the category length $4/5 = 0.8$, 0

1 to less 1.80---very weak, 1.80 to less than 2.60 a few, 2.60 to less than 3.40 medium, 3.40 to less than 4.20 large, 4.20 to 5.00 very large.

Study results

The results of the first question: What are the attitudes of parents towards distance learning for early childhood in light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region?

To answer this question, the arithmetic mean and standard deviations of parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood were extracted in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region, and Table (4) shows this:

Table (4): Arithmetic mean and standard deviations of parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region

#	Domain – Paragraphs	Arithmetic mean	standard deviations	Degree
	Leadership	4.06	.788	large
1	My child's school follows the e-learning strategy approved by the competent authorities	4.22	1.034	Very large
2	My child's teacher strives to update content and activities without violating national laws and policies	4.42	.775	Very large
3	My child's teacher uses e-learning applications efficiently to help the learner achieve international learning standards.	4.02	1.004	large
4	My Child's Teacher provides learner-centered learning opportunities in line with modern educational philosophies.	3.94	1.062	Large
5	My child's teacher uses multiple measurement tools to measure learners' progress.	3.88	1.057	large

6	My child's teacher sets the exact time plan for all the steps that the learner is expected to carry out.	4.01	1.000	Large
7	My child's teacher adheres to the comprehensive assessment criteria for distance learning.	3.97	1.041	Large
	Technology	3.89	.837	Large
8	My child's school provides in its electronic system the electronic alert feature to constantly alert learners	3.64	1.194	Large
9	The teacher encourages my child to use the e-learning system through his smart phone.	3.82	1.147	Large
10	My child's teacher is keen to follow the interaction of learners to obtain data through the distance education system.	4.00	.980	Large
11	My child's teacher uses the right app to deal with slow learners	3.58	1.106	Large
12	My child's teacher carries out the appropriate and required tests through the distance learning system.	4.08	.996	large
13	My child's teacher is keen on how to securely enter the distance learning system	4.23	.894	Very large
	Rehabilitation and support	3.72	.951	Very large
14	My child's teacher encourages me to take advantage of parenting programs in the use of technology and distance learning skills.	3.71	1.110	Large
15	Educational institutions provide training for me in the use of technology and e-learning platforms.	3.43	1.194	Large
16	My child's teacher encourages my child to provide appropriate technical and educational assistance throughout the learning process.	4.02	.980	Large
	the design	4.08	.795	Large
17	My child's teacher is keen to keep the goals of electronic content clear.	4.03	.972	Large
18	My child's teacher adheres to the universal design standards for electronic content.	3.94	.946	Large
19	My child's teacher breaks the content into small, reusable pieces.	4.04	.910	Large
20	My child's teacher provides electronic content in various forms (texts, presentations, audio materials, etc.).	4.22	.940	Very large
21	My child's teacher prepares the content in different designs in terms of color, shape and size, which reduces effort.	4.18	.885	Large
22	My child's teacher presents the electronic educational content in an organized manner and easy to navigate between its parts.	4.25	.798	Very large
23	My child's teacher is keen on evaluating the learners and adding comments on the educational content of the electronic course.	3.92	1.076	Large
	Interaction	4.11	.796	Large
24	My child's teacher encourages him to help him read instructions on how to start using the e-learning system and enter the lessons.	4.09	.984	Large

25	My child's teacher sets the timelines for all the steps that learners are expected to perform for each electronic unit.	4.08	.898	Large
26	My child's teacher is always keen to answer learners' inquiries.	4.15	.973	Large
27	My child's teacher provides feedback to learners on tasks completed on an ongoing basis.	4.18	.913	Large
28	My child's teacher employs self-assessment techniques for learners to check their progress.	4.05	.995	Large
29	My child's teacher employs methods to measure learners' interaction and engagement during the educational presentation.	4.12	.915	Large
	Justice and accessibility	3.93	.908	Large
30	My child's teacher helps me possess the minimum knowledge, technical skills and competencies required to pursue my child in e-learning	3.85	1.028	Large
31	The distance learning system provides my child with access to all programs that serve the learning and education process	3.89	1.036	Large
32	The distance learning system provides my child with easy techniques and ways to get them	3.99	.992	Large
33	The distance learning system allows the presentation of electronic content in multiple audio-visual ways	3.98	1.045	Large
	Measurement and Evaluation	3.78	.938	Large
34	My child's teacher employs learning measurement tools that are appropriate to the activities and resources of electronic content.	4.05	.922	Large
35	The distance learning system clarifies the electronic course evaluation score policy.	3.85	1.089	Large
36	My child's teacher sets descriptive criteria associated with the grading policy for evaluating learner performance.	3.92	.965	Large
37	The distance learning system provides a mechanism to measure the degree of beneficiaries' satisfaction with the e-learning style of providing the material.	3.57	1.288	Large
38	I have the opportunity to evaluate the electronic courses that my son is constantly studying.	3.51	1.307	Large
	total degree	3.97	.746	Large

- It is clear from Table (4) that the attitudes of parents towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region came to a large extent with an arithmetic mean (3.97) and a standard deviation (0.746) the two researchers attribute this to the fact that distance education was the best solution taken by the state after the concerted efforts of several official bodies and the setting up of a huge budget in order to reach the desired goals, continue the learning process, and address the effects that resulted from the Corona pandemic that prevented students from continuing their presence learning , as well as the keenness of parents to invest time and capabilities and continue their children to the process of learning and education.

This study agreed with the study of Basilaia and Kvavadza (2020), and the study of Al-Enezi (2020), which emphasized the keenness of parents to follow up their learning through distance learning systems, and the interaction field ranked first with an arithmetic mean (4.11) and a standard deviation (0.796).) and to a large extent ,The two researchers attribute this to the fact that teachers have an effective role in accustoming the child and the family to electronic education and providing all possible means of communication between the family and the school. This study agreed with the study of Al-Qahtani, Amal, Al-Shehhi, Hayat, Bin Nasser, Alia,

Embassy, Azza (2020). which confirmed the teachers' keenness to communicate and interact with students during distance education and provide them with feedback.

. The design domain ranked second with an arithmetic mean (4.08) and a standard deviation (0.795) with a significant degree, and the leadership domain ranked third with an arithmetic mean (4.06) and a standard deviation (0.788) with a significant degree, The domain of Justice and accessibility ranked fourth with an arithmetic mean (3.93) and a standard deviation (0.908) and with a significant degree, and the field of technology ranked fifth with an arithmetic mean (3.89) and a standard deviation (0.837) with a significant It also ranked sixth in the field of measurement and evaluation with an arithmetic mean (3.78) and a standard deviation (0.938) with a significant large degree, and in the seventh and last rank, the field of rehabilitation and support got an arithmetic mean (3.72) and a standard deviation (0.951) with a significant degree. Although the field of rehabilitation and support ranked last, it came to a large degree, The two researchers attribute this to the fact that all standards were of a high degree of importance from the point of view of parents, as well as from the point of view of those responsible for the learning process who set these standards that contribute to achieving quality and competitiveness.

The results of the second question:

Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level = ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample members about the attitudes of parents towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region according to the variables of type of education, educational stage, Kinship, type of school?

In order to answer this question, the arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample members about parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood were extracted in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region according to the variables of type of education, educational stage, kinship, school type and schedule. (5) Shows that:

Table (5): Averages and standard deviations of parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in Al-Ahsa region according to the variables of type of education, educational stage, kinship, and type of school

variable	Category	Measurement and Evaluation		Justice		Interaction		design		Rehabilitation and support		Technology		Leadership		total degree	
		σ	x	σ	x	σ	x	σ	x	σ	x	σ	x	σ	x	σ	x
education level	Diploma and less	.904	3.86	.690	3.93	.732	4.04	.75	3.92	.999	3.59	.837	3.83	1.02	3.99	.763	3.92
	Bachelor	1.006	3.76	.995	3.88	.798	4.11	.833	4.07	.968	3.71	.857	3.88	.756	4.06	.772	3.96
	Postgraduate	.645	3.75	.660	4.16	.885	4.18	.669	4.21	.840	3.88	.774	4.02	.670	4.16	.622	4.08
educational stage	Kindergarten	.881	3.72	.884	3.96	.776	4.15	.655	4.15	.832	3.65	.805	3.82	.827	4.03	.675	3.96
	primary classes	.978	3.82	.928	3.91	.814	4.09	.877	4.04	1.026	3.76	.859	3.94	.764	4.08	.793	3.97
kinship	Mother	.970	3.78	.897	3.95	.830	4.09	.814	4.06	.934	3.80	.857	3.92	.780	4.09	.769	3.98
	Father	.709	3.90	.600	4.02	.524	4.27	1.047	4.30	.583	3.74	.724	4.07	.734	4.04	.610	4.08
	Other	.950	3.69	1.11	3.80	.782	4.13	.859	4.02	.917	3.35	.799	3.64	.876	3.95	.732	3.84
School type	governmental	.929	3.95	.924	4.00	.821	4.18	.812	4.12	.921	3.80	.828	3.93	.768	4.11	.755	4.04
	Private	.864	3.43	.868	3.79	.734	3.97	.762	4.00	1.0	3.55	.858	3.81	.824	3.96	.714	3.82

It is evident from Table (5) a difference in the arithmetic mean of the responses of the study sample members to the attitudes of parents towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region according to the variables of type of education, educational stage, kinship, type of school and to indicate the significance Differences between arithmetic mean, analysis of variance was used, and table (6) shows that:

Table (6): Analysis of variance of parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in Al-Ahsa region according to the variables of type of education, educational stage, kinship, and type of school

Source of Variance	the Domain	Sum of squares (ss)	Df	Mean squares (MS)	F value	statistically significant
Level	Leadership	.420	2	.210	.330	.719
	Technology	.585	2	.293	.414	.662
	Rehabilitation and Support	1.260	2	.630	.709	.494
	Design	.768	2	.384	.599	.551
	Interaction	.394	2	.197	.306	.737
	Justice and accessibility	1.702	2	.851	1.023	.363
	Measurement and Evaluation	.251	2	.126	.148	.863
	Total marks	.515	2	.257	.458	.634
Stage	Leadership	.002	1	.002	.004	.952
	Technology	.342	1	.342	.483	.488
	Rehabilitation and Support	.061	1	.061	.069	.793
	Design	.711	1	.711	1.109	.294
	Interaction	.554	1	.554	.859	.356
	Justice and accessibility	.304	1	.304	.365	.547
	Measurement and Evaluation	.102	1	.102	.119	.730
	Total degree	.064	1	.064	.113	.737
Kinship	Leadership	.527	2	.264	.414	.662
	Technology	2.112	2	1.056	1.493	.229
	Rehabilitation and Support	4.357	2	2.178	2.451	.090
	Design	.699	2	.349	.545	.581
	Interaction	.307	2	.153	.238	.789
	Justice and accessibility	.582	2	.291	.350	.705
	Measurement and Evaluation	.484	2	.242	.284	.753
	Total degree	.613	2	.306	.545	.581
School	Leadership	.877	1	.877	1.377	.243
	Technology	.387	1	.387	.547	.461
	Rehabilitation and Support	2.313	1	2.313	2.602	.109
	Design	.855	1	.855	1.333	.251
	Interaction	1.655	1	1.655	2.567	.112
	Justice and accessibility	2.132	1	2.132	2.563	.112
	Measurement and Evaluation	7.898	1	7.898	9.282	.003
	Total degree	1.658	1	1.658	2.949	.088
The error	Leadership	78.323	123	.637		
	Technology	86.992	123	.707		
	Rehabilitation and Support	109.318	123	.889		
	Design	78.873	123	.641		
	Interaction	79.295	123	.645		
	Justice and accessibility	102.314	123	.832		
	Measurement and Evaluation	104.661	123	.851		
	Total degree	69.163	123	.562		
Total	Leadership	2225.653	130			
	Technology	2058.583	130			
	Rehabilitation and Support	1913.778	130			
	Design	2246.898	130			
	Interaction	2280.778	130			

	Justice and accessibility	2112.938	130			
	Measurement and Evaluation	1967.880	130			
	Total degree	2118.571	130			

Education level variable:

Table (6) shows that there are no statistically significant differences for parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region on the domains and the total degree according to the educational level variable the two researchers attribute this to the awareness of all parents of different educational levels of the importance of completing the education process for their children, equal opportunities for full-time and working parents in their presence with their children at home, and their conviction that distance learning is the best way to continue the learning process, and this result agreed with the result of Al-Anazi study (2020) with the current study in the absence of statistically significant differences for the educational level variable for parents, and it differed with the Qur'an study (2021), which indicated that there are differences in favor of graduate studies.

Educational stage variable:

Table (6) shows that there are no statistically significant differences in parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in Al-Ahsa region on the domains and the total degree according to the educational stage variable the two researchers attribute this to the parents' awareness of the importance of both stages as it is a stage of establishing all skills and for the convergence of the characteristics of children in both stages, and because e-learning standards are essential and an important reference based on educational institutions in the teaching and learning process.

Kinship variable:

Table (6) shows the absence of statistically significant differences for parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in Al-Ahsa region on the domains and the total degree according to the kinship variable, the two researchers attribute that the family has a key role in the distance education process, as it is the main element in the initiation and continuity of the learning process, and it is the fertile environment for education. Parents are the ones who are keen to provide all appropriate means to follow up the learning process of their children and help them use the techniques used in the distance education system skillfully. Regardless of the relationship with the child, this result is consistent with the result of the study of Malkawi (2020), which indicated that there are no significant differences due to the kinship variable.

School variable:

Table (6) shows that there are no statistically significant differences for parents' attitudes towards distance learning for early childhood in the light of e-learning standards during the Corona pandemic in the Al-Ahsa region on the domains and the total degree according to the school variable except for the seventh domain: Measurement and evaluation and in favor of government education. The two researchers attribute this to the opportunity imposed by the Corona pandemic, which led to changing the culture of Saudi society and its orientation towards distance education, in order to achieve change towards a better future, in addition to the role played by the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

And joint efforts with other parties play a major role in providing appropriate educational platforms for all stages in a short time for public and private education at the same time, in an effort to reach the quality of education. As for the difference that came in the field of measurement and evaluation and in favor of public schools, the researchers attribute this to the care and emphasis taken by the Education Department in the field of measurement and evaluation to include the areas of school leadership, learning methods, educational outcomes and the school environment, and measuring their quality and adequacy through questionnaires, observation, document analysis and interviews, in addition to Providing a mechanism to measure the level of spending efficiency resulting from the delivery of curricula in an e-learning style. This study differs with the study of Al-Quran (2021) in Jordan, which came in favor of private schools.

Recommendations

In light of the results of the study, the researchers recommend the following:

- Providing appropriate courses to develop the technological competence of students, parents and teachers on an ongoing basis to keep abreast of the latest developments in the crisis.
- Implementation of awareness courses that contribute to spreading a positive atmosphere towards distance education.
- Working on continuous updating of the educational content to make it attractive, especially to children of the early childhood stage.

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